

POSSIBLE ANTIAMOEBIIC AGENTS. PART XII. SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED DIALKYLAMINOALKYLAMINOPYRIMIDINES

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Pyrimidines with basic side chains at 2 or 4 position have been prepared for studying their antiamebic activity.

The antimalarial Chloroquin, a 4-aminoquinoline derivative, was introduced as an amœbicide by Conan (*Am. J. Trop. Med.*, 1948, **28**, 107) and Camoquin, a close analogue of Chloroquin, was studied by Hoekenga *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1950, **30**, 625). Like emetine these are selectively absorbed and concentrated in liver tissues, and are therefore useful in the treatment of amœbic hepatitis, although devoid of any significant action in intestinal amœbiasis. Chloroquin having a basic side chain is useful, specially in extra-intestinal amœbiasis. The introduction of the basic side chains to different heterocyclic systems has resulted in the discovery of a number of effective antimalarials, and the promising use of certain antimalarials in the treatment of amœbiasis has prompted a large number of workers to undertake the designing of new potential amœbicides by the introduction of basic side chains to different heterocyclic systems (Elslager *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 469; 1958, **80**, 451; Short *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1958, **80**, 223; Wiley, *ibid.*, 1951, **73**, 4205; Mann and Turnell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 747). The present work has been undertaken to prepare substituted pyrimidines containing basic side chains with the same object.

Two different types of substituted pyrimidines were prepared, viz., 2- γ -dialkylaminoalkylamino-4:6-dihydropyrimidines (I) and 4- γ -dialkylaminoalkylamino-2:6-disubstituted pyrimidines (II), by the condensation of substituted pyrimidines and different dialkylaminopropylamines.

(I)

(II)

$R' = R'' =$ Dialkyl groups.

R_1 & $R_2 =$ Cl, OMe, OEt, and Me.

2- γ -Dialkylaminopropylamino-4:6-dihydropyrimidines were obtained by the condensation of 2-methylthio-4:6-dihydropyrimidine and five different dialkylaminopropylamines at 170°, following the method of King and King (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 725). The reaction took place with evolution of methylthiol and a gummy product was obtained, which was purified by extraction with ethanol.

4- γ -Dialkylaminopropylamino-2: 6-disubstituted pyrimidines were prepared by the direct condensation of 4-chloro-2: 6-disubstituted (chloro, methoxy, ethoxy and methyl) pyrimidines and different amines, either in acetone or in absolute ethanol for 4 to 12 hours. Hydrochlorides were obtained by adding dry ether to the residue obtained after removing ethanol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dialkylaminopropionitriles were obtained by refluxing the appropriate secondary amines with acrylonitrile on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The mixture was left overnight and purified by distillation under reduced pressure (Whitmore *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 777): β -Dipropylⁿaminopropionitrile, b.p. 102°/8mm; β -dibutylⁿaminopropionitrile, b.p. 127°/6mm; β -diamylⁿaminopropionitrile, b.p. 152°/6mm; β -morpholinopropionitrile, b.p. 130°/4mm; β -piperidinopropionitrile, b.p. 125-28°/5mm.

Dialkylaminopropylamines.—The nitriles, thus obtained, were reduced catalytically at 60 lb. pressure using Raney nickel, following the method of Holcomb and Hamilton (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1309). It is interesting to note that γ -piperidinopropylamine, which has been obtained by high pressure hydrogenation (Whitmore *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), is easily obtained at 60 lb. pressure in 65% yield.

γ -Dipropylⁿaminopropylamine, b.p. 77-80°/5mm; γ -dibutylⁿaminopropylamine, b.p. 115-16°/12mm; γ -diamylⁿaminopropylamine, b.p. 125°/5mm; γ -morpholinopropylamine, b.p. 225°/7-8 mm; γ -piperidinopropylamine, b.p. 204-209°/748mm.

Substituted Pyrimidines.—The starting materials, barbituric acid and thiobarbituric acid, were obtained according to the methods given in the literature ("Org. Synthesis", Vol. II, p. 60; Michael, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1894, *ii*, **49**, 38).

2-Methylthiobarbituric acid was prepared by the action of methyl sulphate on thiobarbituric acid in sodium bicarbonate solution (King and King, *loc. cit.*).

2: 4: 6-Trichloropyrimidine was prepared from barbituric acid according to Gabriel (*Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 3666) by heating with POCl_3 in presence of dimethylaniline. It was distilled at 211-13°/750mm.

2-Methoxy-4: 6-dichloropyrimidine and 2: 6-dimethoxy-4-chloropyrimidine were prepared from 2: 4: 6-trichloropyrimidine by the action of sodium in methanol under cooling (Buttner, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 2234).

6-Ethoxy-2: 4-dichloropyrimidine was also obtained from 2: 4: 6-trichloropyrimidine, sodium, and ethanol by following the method of Winkelmann (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1927, *ii*, **115**, 310).

6-Methyl-2: 4-dichloropyrimidine was prepared from 6-methyluracil ("Org. Synthesis", Vol. II, p. 422) by the action of POCl_3 in presence of dimethylaniline according to the method of Gabriel and Colman (*Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 1532).

2- γ -Dialkylaminopropylamino-4: 6-dihydroxypyrimidines.—Five new 2- γ -dialkylaminopropylamino-4: 6-dihydroxypyrimidines were synthesised by the condensation of 2-methylthiobarbituric acid (0.01 M) and the corresponding amines (0.01 M) at 170° (oil bath). The reaction took place with evolution of methylthiol. When no more of methylthiol was evolved, the reaction

mixture was cooled, the product dissolved in ethanol and filtered to remove 2-methylthiobarbituric acid. On distilling off ethanol under reduced pressure the gummy residue was recrystallised from a mixture of acetone and ethanol. As the picrates of these compounds were found to be oily, picrolonates were prepared in the usual way, and recrystallised from absolute ethanol. The m.p., yield, analysis, etc. are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

R' and R''	Hydroxypyrimidines.			M.P.	Picrolonates.		
	M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.		Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.	
R ₁ & R ₂ =4:6-dihydroxy.							
Di-Pr ⁿ -	282°	74	23.01 22.95	210°	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ O ₇ N ₈	21.21 21.05	
Di-Bu ⁿ -	287°	71	18.86 18.91	192-93°	C ₃₃ H ₅₄ O ₇ N ₈	19.78 20.00	
Di-Am ⁿ -	> 300°	86	16.95 17.28	157°	C ₂₇ H ₄₀ O ₇ N ₈	18.85 19.04	
Morpholino-	147°	63	21.90 22.22	182-84°	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₈	21.74 21.62	
Piperidino-	231°	75	21.90 22.04	198°	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₇ N ₈	21.52 21.70	

Compounds No. 1 to 5 melted with decomposition.

TABLE II

R ₁ and R ₂	R' and R''	Chloropyrimidines.			M.P.	Picrates.		
		M.P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.		Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.	
2:6-Dichloro	Di-Pr ⁿ -	152°	64	17.52 17.63	137°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₇ N ₇ Cl ₂	18.00 18.35	
"	Di-Bu ⁿ -	128°	57	15.66 15.42	..	..	..	
"	Morpholino-	126°	37	16.85 17.09	..	..	..	
"	Piperidino-	174°	46	16.71 17.20	..	..	..	
2-Methoxy-6-chloro	Morpholino-	178°	56	17.10 17.39	..	..	..	
"	Piperidino-	207°	61	17.12 17.44	..	..	..	
2:6-Dimethoxy	Morpholino-	176°	63	17.32 17.58	200°	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ N ₇	18.75 19.17	
*2-Chloro-6-ethoxy	Piperidino-	135-36°	59	16.73 16.91	155-56°	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₇ Cl	18.62 18.57	
"	Morpholino-	..	77	16.32 16.61	199°	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₇ Cl	18.47 18.71	
"	Di-Am ⁿ -	252-53°	39°	13.37 13.76	..	..	..	
*2-Chloro-6-methyl	Morpholino-	..	78	17.99 18.24	147°	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₇ Cl	19.43 19.81	
"	Piperidino-	146°	65	18.12 18.36	158°	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₇ N ₇ Cl	19.58 19.90	
"	Di-Am ⁿ -	232°	19	14.43 14.85	..	..	..	

Compounds are very hygroscopic *

4-γ-Dialkylaminopropylamino-2:6-dichloropyrimidines.— The appropriate amine (0.005 M) in acetone (5 c.c.) was added dropwise to a solution of trichloropyrimidine in little acetone under stirring and cooling. The monohydrochlorides separated as a crystalline mass within 15 to 20 minutes or after little concentration and cooling, and these were recrystallised from dry acetone.

4- γ -Dialkylaminopropylamino-(2-methoxy-6-chloro-, -2:6-dimethoxy-, -2-chloro-6-ethoxy-, and -2-chloro-6-methyl)-pyrimidines were prepared by the following method: A mixture of 4-chloro-2:6-disubstituted pyrimidine (0.005 *M*) and γ -dialkylaminopropylamine (0.005 *M*) in 15 c.c. absolute ethanol was refluxed for 4 to 12 hours. Completion of reaction was noticed by a change of colour in the reaction mixture. Alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and dry ether was added to the residues. The monohydrochlorides separating out as crystalline solids were filtered, washed with dry ether and recrystallised from absolute ethanol, petroleum ether, benzene or dry acetone as required. Compounds * (Table II) did not give a sharp m.p. as being very hygroscopic. These were characterised as their picrates.

The m.p., yields, analysis, etc. of dialkylaminoalkylamino-substituted pyrimidines, their hydrochlorides, picrolonates, and picrates are reported in Table II.

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